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One-pot nitrodebromination and methyl bi-functionalization of 5-bromo 6-methylpyrimidines: a unique simultaneous transformation

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Abstract

A unique one-pot, simultaneous nitrodebromination and methyl bromonitration occurred upon treatment of 5-bromo-2,4-di-*tert*-amino-6-methylpyrimidine derivatives with a cold mixture of concentrated H₂SO₄-HNO₃ in moderate yields. It is actually a facile and rapid transformation that has been reported neither on pyrimidines nor simultaneously on other organic compounds.

Keywords: Additive free, Bromonitration, Catalyst free, Gem-broonitromethyl pyrimidine, Nitrodebromination